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IEA Wind TCP Task 43

Evolving the wind energy sector towards frictionless and sustainable data usage

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Authors:

Thomas Clark
Octue

Julian Quick
DTU Wind

Des Farren
ServusNet

Anna Maria Sempreviva
DTU Wind

Shawn Sheng
National Renewable Energy Laboratory

Sarah Barber
Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences

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Executive Summary

In this report, we highlight the steps in the evolution of the wind energy sector towards frictionless and sustainable data usage, and provide organisations with concrete suggestions for how to focus and prioritise their efforts. We understand frictionless and sustainable data usage to mean “removing data usage barriers between different stakeholders and between data lifecycle stages in the long-term”. We see frictionless and sustainable data usage as an important component of unlocking the full value of wind energy through digital transformation, which is the goal of IEA Wind Task 43. Frictionless and sustainable data usage is key for increasing data maturity, and for ultimately creating intelligent, automated, scalable AI-based systems for increasing the value and impact of wind energy.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this report is to highlight the steps in the evolution of the wind energy sector towards frictionless and sustainable data usage, and provide organisations with concrete suggestions for how to focus and prioritise their efforts. We understand frictionless and sustainable data usage to mean “removing data usage barriers between different stakeholders and between data lifecycle stages in the long-term”. We see frictionless and sustainable data usage as an important component of unlocking the full value of wind energy through digital transformation, which is the goal of IEA Wind Task 43. Frictionless and sustainable data usage is key for increasing data maturity, and for ultimately creating intelligent, automated, scalable AI-based systems for increasing the value and impact of wind energy.

1.2 Background information on Task 43 and this report

In IEA Wind Task 43, our vision is to unlock the full value of wind energy through digital transformation. Our mission is to act as a digital transformation catalyst by driving open collaboration within and beyond the wind community to deliver insights, recommendations, standards and tools in the key areas of data, culture, and cooperation. Our activities are based on the three “[Grand challenges in the digitalisation of wind energy](#)”, Data, Culture and Cooperation. Cooperation refers to competition or cooperation between organisations.

The report is based on the collaborative R&D which was undertaken in the publication of the above-mentioned paper, “[Grand challenges in the digitalisation of wind energy](#)”, involving interviews, surveys and literature reviews about the challenges and opportunities of digitalisation in wind energy.

1.3 Summary of the contents

This report consists of a short presentation that was prepared in order to provide concise, applicable and understandable guidelines to organisations wanting to fully exploit the value of their data. Following the title page, we explain the purpose of the document, introduce our suggestions for three steps that can be taken, what the steps facilitate and which benefits they lead to. Finally, we define the most important terms.

1.4 Contributors

As well as the authors, Thomas Clark from Octue, Julian Quick from DTU Wind, Des Farren from ServusNet, Anna Maria Sempreviva from DTU Wind, Shawn Sheng from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory and Sarah Barber from the Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences, a large number of IEA Wind Task 43 participants and collaborators have contributed to this report. In particular, the reviews from Faiz Sulaiman (Microsoft), Manuel João Almeida (Vestas), Jeff Clerc (NREL), Sakshi Sircar (SSE Renewables), Phil Bradstock (Bitbloom), Stuart Chalk (University of Florida), and Christian Johnsson (KUDO) were essential. Contributions from the

members of the IEA Wind Task 43 Organising Committee Yu Ding (Georgia Tech), Stephen Holleran (Brightwind), Nikolay Dimitrov (DTU Wind) and Gibson Kersting (RWE) were key for setting and maintaining the overall strategic direction of the document.

1.5 Intended audience

The intended audience is any person interested in removing data usage barriers between different stakeholders and between data lifecycle stages in the long-term within or beyond their organisation in the wind energy sector.

1.6 Intended benefit or usefulness of report

By taking the suggested steps, organisations can evolve towards frictionless and sustainable data usage, which is essential to unlocking the full value of wind energy through digital transformation

1.7 Special acknowledgments

Special thanks to the former Co-Operating Agents of IEA Wind Task 43, Jason Fields (formerly NREL) and Berthold Hahn (formerly Fraunhofer IEE), who initiated the creation of this report.

2. Main Body of Report

The main body of the report can be found in the next six slides.

Evolving the wind energy sector towards frictionless and sustainable data usage

May 2025

Purpose of this document

With this document, we aim to highlight the steps in the evolution of the wind energy sector towards **frictionless and sustainable data usage**, and provide organisations with concrete suggestions for how to focus and prioritise their efforts.

We understand **frictionless and sustainable data usage** to mean “removing data usage barriers between different stakeholders and between data lifecycle stages in the long-term.” This can include the FAIR data principles and beyond.

We see **frictionless and sustainable data usage** as an important component of unlocking the full value of wind energy through digital transformation, which is the goal of IEA Wind Task 43. **Frictionless and sustainable data usage** is key for increasing data maturity, and for ultimately creating intelligent, automated, scalable AI-based systems for increasing the value and impact of wind energy.

This document was created by a team of volunteers working in the wind energy sector as part of IEA Wind Task 43.

Evolving the wind energy sector towards frictionless and sustainable data usage

What you can do:

*“1. Start by **structuring data** according to a (industry-standard, where possible) **schema**, to deliver immediate impact and capture engineering knowledge and experience.”*

*“2. Transition to **more sophisticated knowledge engineering systems** comprising ontology-driven knowledge graphs, FAIR principles and **community-defined semantic artefacts**.”*

*“3. Leverage the full benefits of **deep, nonlinear workflows** to reach frictionless and sustainable data usage for complex use cases that involve **uncertainty**, and create **natural language interfaces** for accessing data.”*

This facilitates...

Creating static automated workflows

Creating processes for the exchange of data and services

Implementing dynamic data discovery and translation systems

Creating dynamic workflows that include data-driven optimisation solutions

Creating intelligent ensembles and optimised workflows in the face of uncertainty

Making these workflows sustainably accessible and usable for end users

And leads to these benefits...

Deliver immediate and profound commercial value

Via quicker time to market (e.g. to break ground on new farms), reduced risk (auditability / accountability), reduced internal overhead and maintaining profitable scalability.

De-risk and reduce collaboration overhead

Via reduced communication overhead and manual transformation and ability to engage external stakeholders.

Resolve heterogeneous processes

With the ability to operate on semi-structured data, workflows can be consolidated fleet-wide and enable consistent comparison as well as greatly reduced data management burden.

Deeper insight

With the ability to operate on semi-structured data, workflows can incorporate far more diverse datasets.

Make performance guarantees and reduce risk

Be able to deliver guarantees on performance and reduce project planning risk based on improved confidence.

Save time and increase efficiency of downstream tasks

Allow end users to use deep nonlinear workflows to increase their efficiency in solving existing problems and to adapt them in order to solve new problems.

Definitions (page 1/2)

Dynamic data discovery and translation	The process of finding and identifying data, typically in semi-structured form and from diverse and heterogeneous sources, and reliably translating or interpreting that data to meet a structured form suitable for use in a workflow.
Dynamic workflows	Workflows that can adapt and change to account for heterogeneous inputs, conditions, or real-time data, allowing for flexible execution paths.
FAIR principles	Guidelines for making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
Intelligent ensembling	The ability to combine results of models (or outputs of workflows) whose input data sources, underlying assumptions, methods and uncertainties are heterogeneous, in order to reduce overall uncertainty.
Knowledge graph	A rich, interconnected representation of data, which enables advanced functionalities such as executing semantic queries (aiming to understand the meaning and context), reasoning through logical inferences, and uncovering insights from relationships across diverse datasets.
Ontology	A structured framework that defines the concepts, relationships, and categories within a specific domain to enable shared understanding and data interoperability.

Definitions (page 2/2)

Schema	A formal structure that defines how data is organised, including the types of data elements and the relationships between them.
Semi-structured data	Data which: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- has missing elements but is otherwise compliant with the requirements of a schema, OR- meets requirements of a schema but extends to add extra information, OR- is unstructured (or is structured but in a different form) and whose contents, potentially from diverse sources, could be reliably used (eg translated or interpreted) to generate a structured form.
Semantic artefact	A machine-actionable formalisation (represented using appropriate formats and serialisations) of a conceptualisation, enabling sharing and reuse by humans and machines, whereby “serialisation” refers to converting data or an object into a format that can be easily stored or transmitted.
Workflow	A defined sequence of tasks or processes that data flows through, from ingestion to transformation and output, often involving both automated steps and points of human intervention. In the context of slide 4, a deep, nonlinear workflow refers to a workflow with many layers or steps that do not follow a simple, step-by-step progression.

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*Thank you very much for reading,
and good luck on your journey!*

*Tom Clark, Julian Quick, Des Farren,
Anna Maria Sempreviva, Shawn Sheng,
Sarah Barber*

3. Conclusions

In this report, we have highlighted the steps in the evolution of the wind energy sector towards frictionless and sustainable data usage, and provided organisations with concrete suggestions for how to focus and prioritise their efforts. We understand frictionless and sustainable data usage to mean “removing data usage barriers between different stakeholders and between data lifecycle stages in the long-term”. We see frictionless and sustainable data usage as an important component of unlocking the full value of wind energy through digital transformation, which is the goal of IEA Wind Task 43. Frictionless and sustainable data usage is key for increasing data maturity, and for ultimately creating intelligent, automated, scalable AI-based systems for increasing the value and impact of wind energy. Special thanks to the former Co-Operating Agents of IEA Wind Task 43, Jason Fields (formerly NREL) and Berthold Hahn (formerly Fraunhofer IEE), who initiated the creation of this report.